

Feedback Controlled Magnetic Levitation for Measuring Small Force/Torque and Micro-Positioning

Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the degree of
Master of Technology

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2019

Approval Sheet

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Acknowledgement

I want to express my thanks to my guide, Prof. Kantimay Das Gupta, for his guidance and support for this project. The entire planning of my work is supervised by him, and it has been a great opportunity for me to work under his guidance. He helped me a lot in directing and assisting properly for successful completion of this project. The reference material that he provided has been valuable.

I would also like to thank Dr. Shilpi Pandey (Biosciences & Bioengineering Department, IIT Bombay) and Prof. Pradeep Sarin (Department of Physics, IIT Bombay) for their support, help, and assistance for completion of the project.

The members of Prof. Kantimay Das Gupta's lab who guided and helped me with the understanding of this project.

Abstract

In this project report, we start the discussion in brief about equilibrium (mechanical) and the conditions for stable and unstable equilibrium. Then we discuss the stability of levitation and the conditions required for proper levitation of different kind of objects (a permanent magnet, paramagnetic and diamagnetic) in the magnetic field. To achieve stable equilibrium with permanent magnets, we introduced a feedback mechanism in the system and simulated the potential energy of the magnetic dipole (in static conditions) in the presence of an electromagnet with and without the feedback mechanism.

We then verified the working of the feedback circuit and observed successful levitation of a permanent magnet. We also develop a simple model based on the equations of motion of the particle and MOSFET equations. We simulated these equations with the RK-4 method, with an adaptive time-step. All the parameters used were equal to the real values used in the experiment. We performed the experiments in atmospheric conditions as well as in low-pressure conditions (at 25KPa). We tried to improve the feedback circuit from a simple proportional to PID and observe the changes. We also included a brief discussion about the various uses of this set-up and the kind of experiment and analysis to be done in the future.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Mechanical Equilibrium

Equilibrium (mechanical) is the state of a system in which all the competing forces are balanced, i.e., the net force is zero. If the system gets displaced from its equilibrium state by any perturbation then comes the question: whether this equilibrium was stable (comes back to the equilibrium state), unstable (moves further away from the equilibrium state) or neutral (neither tends to return nor move away from the equilibrium state)?

Figure 1.1: Direction of Force as we move from equilibrium point

Mathematically, for equilibrium to occur force $\vec{F} = 0$ i.e. $\vec{\nabla}U = 0$, where U is the potential energy of the system.

For a system to be in stable equilibrium the restoring force should be in opposite direction of displacement, as shown in fig. 1.1 i.e. $\nabla^2 U < 0$ at the equilibrium point. Therefore for a stable equilibrium:

$$\nabla^2 U > 0 \quad \because (\vec{F} = -\vec{\nabla}U)$$

Similarly, for an unstable equilibrium we have:

$$\nabla^2 U < 0$$

1.2 Levitation

Levitation essentially means to hold an object afloat without any mechanical support. Under laboratory conditions, there will be many small perturbations like air drag, etc. So for levitation to occur in a good way, the state of equilibrium in this condition should be stable.

The best way to achieve levitation, as of now, is by using magnetic force [1] [2] [3]. The force on a dipole in a magnetic field is given by [4]:

$$\vec{F} = \vec{\nabla}(\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B}) \quad (1.1)$$

As we know $\vec{F} = -\vec{\nabla}U$, we have:

$$\Rightarrow U = -\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B} \quad (1.2)$$

Figure 1.2: Representation of Stable, Unstable and Neutral Equilibrium

For a constant dipole μ . We have:

$$\vec{F} = -\vec{\nabla}U \quad (1.3)$$

$$\Rightarrow \vec{F} = \vec{\nabla}(\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B}) \quad (1.4)$$

$$\Rightarrow \vec{F} = \mu_x \left[\frac{\partial B_x}{\partial x} \hat{i} + \mu_y \frac{\partial B_y}{\partial y} \hat{j} + \mu_z \frac{\partial B_z}{\partial z} \hat{k} \right] \quad (1.5)$$

At equilibrium $F = 0$. For the state of equilibrium we need to know the sign of $\nabla^2 U$.

$$\nabla^2 U = -\nabla^2(\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B}) \quad (1.6)$$

$$\Rightarrow \nabla^2 U = -\vec{\mu} \cdot (\nabla^2 \vec{B}) \quad (1.7)$$

We know that in free space $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = 0$ [4].

$$\Rightarrow \vec{\nabla} \times (\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B}) = 0 \quad (1.8)$$

$$\Rightarrow \vec{\nabla}(\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B}) - \nabla^2 \vec{B} = 0 \quad (1.9)$$

From gauss's law we know that divergence of magnetic field is 0.

$$\Rightarrow \nabla^2 \vec{B} = 0 \quad (1.10)$$

$$\Rightarrow \nabla^2 U = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

So for constant dipole μ , $\nabla^2 U = 0$. This is not a stable equilibrium condition [5].

For diamagnetic or paramagnetic materials, the dipole is given by $\mu = CB$, where $C = \frac{\chi V}{\mu_0}$ We have:

$$U = -\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B} \quad (1.12)$$

$$\Rightarrow U = -C\vec{B} \cdot \vec{B} \quad (1.13)$$

$$\Rightarrow \nabla^2 U = -C\vec{\nabla} \cdot (\vec{\nabla}(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{B})) \quad (1.14)$$

$$\Rightarrow \nabla^2 U = -C\vec{\nabla} \cdot (\vec{\nabla}(|B|^2)) \quad (1.15)$$

$$\Rightarrow \nabla^2 U = -2C\vec{\nabla} \cdot \left[B_i \frac{\partial B_i}{\partial x_j} \hat{e}_j \right] \quad (1.16)$$

$$\Rightarrow \nabla^2 U = -2C \left[\left(\frac{\partial B_i}{\partial x_j} \right)^2 + B_i \frac{\partial^2 B_i}{\partial x_j^2} \right] \quad (1.17)$$

$$\Rightarrow \nabla^2 U = -2C \left[\left(\frac{\partial B_i}{\partial x_j} \right)^2 \right] \quad \because (\nabla^2 \vec{B} = 0) \quad (1.18)$$

χ is the magnetic susceptibility, V is the volume. Thus the stability depends on the sign of C ([some positive number] $\times \chi$). So we have an unstable equilibrium for paramagnetic materials and a stable equilibrium for diamagnetic materials [6].

As we know, we need a stable equilibrium for a good levitating system, but from the analysis, it is clear that stable equilibrium is possible only if we use diamagnetic materials in free space. In recent years scientists have extensively used diamagnetic levitation for different applications like weightless fluid dynamics, container-less crystal growth, low friction bearings, high precision gyroscopes, high sensitive sensors, etc. [7] Diamagnetic levitation has been used with large ultra-high field electromagnets to demonstrate levitation of natural organisms.

It becomes clear from the above arguments that we need a feedback mechanism [8] if we want to achieve levitation for a normal magnet or paramagnetic materials[9].

Chapter 2

Feedback Circuit

2.1 Proportional Feedback

Figure 2.1: Proportional Feedback Circuit Diagram. Voltage Regulator:- 7808; Photo-Transistor:- OP550A; MOSFET:- STP16NF06

Feedback used in this experiment is simple proportional feedback. The LED's are placed below the coil on the LED stand. The position of the object is sensed using these two LED's, as the object blocks the light between LED's and the photo-transistor.

Let's assume that z_a is the distance of the top part of the LED from the coil and z_b is the distance of the bottom part of the LED from the coil. So we have a range of operation of feedback as $z_b - z_a$ (as shown in fig. 2.2).

In this feedback circuit, when the top surface of the object is at z_a , the current through the coil is 0. And when the top surface of the object is at z_b , the current through the coil is max.

Figure 2.2: Balancing the object between z_a and z_b , at z_0

Let's assume the top surface of the object is balanced at a distance z_0 from the coil and

$$z_a < z_0 < z_b$$

If a small perturbation (δ) is applied to the object towards the coil. The new position of the top surface of the object is now $z_0 - \delta$, this blocks more light compared to when the position was z_0 , which in turn reduces the light falling on a phototransistor. As a result of which the current through the photo-transistor decreases, which decreases the gate voltage of MOSFET. When the gate voltage decreases, the drain current across drain and source will also decrease. Now, this drain current passes through the coil, thus when the drain current decreases, the magnetic field produced by the coil will also decrease. Therefore the net force now is away from the coil and towards z_0 (as seen in fig. 2.3)

The opposite effect is seen when the perturbation is δ away from the coil, i.e., $z = z_0 + \delta$, in this situation, the net force acts towards z_0 which can be seen as a point of stable equilibrium.

Figure 2.3: Effect of feedback circuit: changing from an unstable to stable equilibrium

2.2 PID Feedback

Here the circuit is upgraded from a simple proportional circuit to a PID. The position sensing mechanism and the general behavior of the feedback are still similar to the proportional circuit. PID is being used to improve on the stability and to suppress the oscillations produced in the previous circuit.

Figure 2.4: Proportional Integral Differentiator (PID) Feedback Circuit Diagram. Voltage Regulator: 7808; Photo-Transistor: OP550A; Quad Op-Amp: IL074CN; Dual Op-Amp: OPA2277P; MOSFET: IRF520

Chapter 3

Basic Model

3.1 Static Equilibrium

3.1.1 Without Feedback

Figure 3.1: Orientation of the coil and $z = 0$ point.

The axial magnetic field of a solenoid is an elementary calculation, and it gives a fairly accurate measurement of magnetic strength at a certain point along the axis of the coil. The magnetic field at a point z from the base of the coil, as shown in fig. 3.1, is given by [10]:

$$B = \frac{\mu_0 n i}{2} \left\{ \frac{L + z}{((L + z)^2 + a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{z}{(z^2 + a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right\} \quad (3.1)$$

where n is the number of turns per unit length, i is current through the coil, L is length of the coil and a is radius of the coil.

Let's assume the direction given by acceleration due to gravity is positive. On a permanent magnet with dipole moment $\vec{\mu}$, the force would be:

$$F = mg + \vec{\nabla}(\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B}) \quad (3.2)$$

Where B is the magnetic field, m is mass of magnet, and g is acceleration due to gravity. If the dipole is placed on the axis of a solenoid in such a way that they attract each other, then the potential energy is given by:

$$U = -mgz - \vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B} \quad (3.3)$$

If dipole and solenoid attract each other then the dipole and magnetic field are in the same direction i.e. $\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B} = \mu B$.

$$\Rightarrow U = -mgz - \mu B \quad (3.4)$$

$$\Rightarrow U = -mgz - \frac{\mu\mu_0 ni}{2} \left\{ \frac{L+z}{((L+z)^2 + a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{z}{(z^2 + a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right\} \quad (3.5)$$

Figure 3.2: Graph of Potential Energy vs distance form coil

Fig. 3.2 shows how potential energy varies along the axis of the coil as we move away from it. It can be seen that there is a point of unstable equilibrium in this system, which means that, in this set-up, without feedback, levitation is impossible to achieve.

3.1.2 With Proportional Feedback

To achieve levitation by attraction, we need some feedback. In this part of the project, we give simple proportional feedback to the circuit. As seen from fig. 2.2, the feedback can be seen as:

$$i = i_0 \frac{z - z_a}{z_b - z_a} \quad (3.6)$$

Where i is current in the coil and i_0 is maximum current that can flow through the coil. This feedback gives no current when the photo-transistor is completely blocked, i.e., at $z = z_a$, maximum current when it's fully exposed to the LEDs, i.e., at $z = z_b$ and changes linearly, as shown by equation (3.6) when the object is between z_a and z_b . So the new potential energy can be given as:

$$U = -mgz - \frac{\mu\mu_0 n}{2} \left\{ i_0 \frac{z - z_a}{z_b - z_a} \right\} \left\{ \frac{L+z}{((L+z)^2 + a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{z}{(z^2 + a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right\} \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.3: Graph of Potential Energy vs distance form coil

The moment feedback is switched on, potential energy curve changes. This feedback depends on the values of i_0 , z_a and z_b . Equation (3.7) was simulated with similar parameters as used for fig. 3.2 and a set of values for i_0 , z_a and z_b . The result of feedback can be seen in fig. 3.3. A potential well, the signature of stable equilibrium, has developed as a result of turning on the feedback. This local stability will help in achieving levitation.

3.2 Dynamic Equilibrium

Figure 3.4: Circuit of photo-transistor and MOSFET in feedback.

From fig. 3.4 across MOSFET we have:

$$V_{dd} - I_d R - L \frac{dI_d}{dt} - V_{DS} = 0 \quad (3.8)$$

(assuming that the resistance between S and 0 is 0)

Where V_{DS} is the voltage across Drain and Source. And we know from MOSFET equa-

tions that V_{DS} is a function of Drain current I_d and voltage across Gate and Source V_{GS} [11]. And V_{GS} is a function of I_l as:

$$V_{GS} = I_l R_f \quad (3.9)$$

Also I_l is the current through photo-transistor which depends on the position of the object, z , which is given by equation (3.6). As the system is dynamic, the object is also moving. The object is attracted by the magnetic field of coil and pulled down by force of gravity. Its equation of motion is given by:(using equation (1.1) for the force between magnet and coil)

$$m\ddot{z} = m\vec{g} + \vec{\nabla}(\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B}(I_d, z)) \quad (3.10)$$

The magnetic field $\vec{B}(I_d, z)$ is given by equation (3.1). Thus the self-consistent solutions of equation (3.8) and (3.10) will give us a better understanding of the parameters at which the system of equations is stable and in turn, the object can levitate under the influence of feedback.

Chapter 4

Simulating Dynamic Equations

Using equation (3.8) and (3.10) we can form the set of equations that govern the motion of the particle.

$$\frac{dI_d}{dt} = \frac{1}{L} [V_{dd} - I_d R - V_{DS}] \quad (4.1)$$

$$\dot{p} = g + \frac{\mu}{m} \nabla(B(I_d, z)) \quad (4.2)$$

$$\dot{z} = p \quad (4.3)$$

Where $\vec{B}(I_d, z)$ is given by equation (3.1).

V_{DS} depends upon I_d and V_{GS} (Gate-Source Voltage) and the following equation was the best fit after studying the graphs in the MOSFET data-sheet:

$$V_{DS} = t_2 \left[\ln \left\{ \frac{a_1 \left(1 - \exp \left(-\frac{(V_{GS} - V_{th})^y}{t_1} \right) \right)}{a_1 \left(1 - \exp \left(-\frac{(V_{GS} - V_{th})^y}{t_1} \right) \right) - I_d} \right\} \right] \quad (4.4)$$

where a_1 , t_1 , t_2 and y are constants that are used to best fit the curve given in the data-sheet.

Gate-Source Voltage or V_{GS} is given using equations (3.6) and (3.9):

$$V_{GS} = I_0 R_f \frac{z - z_a}{z_b - z_a} \quad (4.5)$$

where z_a and z_b are the beginning and end position of the feedback respectively.

Figure 4.1: (a): Output characteristic of MOSFET (STP16NF06) from the data-sheet. (b): Output characteristic using the fit equation (eq. (4.4)).

These set of equations i.e. from (4.1) - (4.5) were simulated using Runge-Kutta 4 method. To get closer to a real system, a noise term was also added in equation (4.2); we tried to vary this parameter as well. It was of the form $noise = nf * rand$, where nf is the noise multiplication factor (or simply noise factor), and $rand$ is a random number generated between -1 and 1.

4.1 Results

Values of all the parameters in the equations (4.1) - (4.5) were used close to the real values used in the experiments to get a better idea about the system. The only parameter that was varied was the mass (m) of the suspended object.

A more detailed run of these simulations was done by varying the mass of the object by 1 g starting from 50 g up to 90 g, the variation of frequency with mass was observed and plotted as shown in fig. 4.3.

4.1.1 Changing Mass value

Figure 4.2: Simulation result for mass = 50g (a): Position vs Time data between $t=20$ s to $t=22$ s. (b): FFT of the data in part (a).

We then made a \log_e plot of peak frequencies vs mass of the levitated object as shown in fig. 4.6. As we tried to fit the graph using a linear function, the slope of came out to be

-0.45. So from these simulations, we can say that:

$$f \propto \frac{1}{m^{0.45}} \quad (4.6)$$

Figure 4.3: Log plot of frequency vs mass.

4.1.2 Changing Noise factor

The mass of the object was kept constant, and by changing the noise factor term, the noise in the system was varied. The simulations gave the following results.

Figure 4.4: Simulation result for $nf = 0$

Figure 4.6: Simulation result for $nf = 0.01$

As we increase the noise factor in the simulations, the amplitude of oscillations increase. After a certain value of nf the object begins oscillations at $t = 0$, but after some time it falls i.e., z stops oscillating, and it just increases with time.

Figure 4.7: Simulation result for $nf = 0.05$

Chapter 5

Experimental Set-up

(a) Coil

(b) Coil Stand

(c) Coil Support

(d) L-Clamp

(e) LED Stand

(f) Suspended Object

Figure 5.1: Components used in the experiment, as shown in figure, were designed using SolidWorks. (f) was 3-D printed

Figure 5.2: (a): Coil; (b): LEDs; (c): Opening to Photo-transistor; (d): Suspended Object; (e): Scale

Figure 5.3: (a): Coil; (b): LEDs; (c): Opening to Photo-transistor; (d): Suspended Object; (e): Scale

The winding of the electromagnetic coil used in the set-up is done by hand. The following parameters of the coil were measured (after winding):

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Number of turns per unit length} &= 13143m^{-1} \\ \text{Inductance} &= 30mH \\ \text{Resistane} &= 12\Omega\end{aligned}$$

As shown in fig. 5.2 and fig. 5.3, it can be observed that the object is indeed levitating. It blocks the light from LED to the photo-transistor (proportional feedback) and balances itself at a particular height.

Fig. 5.4 shows the set-up for the low-pressure system. The top of the desiccator is attached to a vacuum pump using a valve opening as shown in fig. 5.4a. We switch on the pump to remove the air inside the system such that the pressure comes down to $25KPa$.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.4: Low-Pressure Set-up. (a): With closed lid and pump. (b): With open lid.

Chapter 6

Experimental Results

The levitating object has a small magnet at the end, and a pick-up coil is placed below the object such that the magnet can move inside the coil. With this set-up, we can record the small fluctuations about a mean position but not the actual z-position.

As the levitating object oscillates, the magnetic field inside the coil will change due to the presence of a moving magnet. These oscillations will produce an emf across the two ends of the wire. We record this emf value after passing the signal through a pre-amplifier with a gain and a cut-off frequency.

6.1 Small Oscillations

Figure 6.1: (a): Coil; (b): LEDs; (c): Opening to Photo-transistor; (d): Suspended Object; (e): Detector Coil

Figure 6.2: (a): Data after passing through a preamp with gain 100 with cut-off value of 10kHz at 6dB. (b): FFT of the data in part (a). (c): Data after passing through a preamp with gain 100 with cut-off value of 30kHz at 6dB. (d): FFT of the data in part (d).

6.2 Damping

A small perturbation was given to the system (a small tap to the table on which the experiment was set-up). In the starting part of fig. 6.3a, we can see a sudden appearance of oscillations. As time progresses, from fig. 6.3a towards the end of fig. 6.3b, dampens and finally dies down. From these observations, we can conclude that the feedback system is doing its job well.

Figure 6.3: (a): Oscillations as we disturb the system. (b): Damping of signal as we move from (a) to (b) as the oscillations die down and mixes with the noise.

6.3 Varying Mass of the Object

The data was taken by placing a coil surrounding the levitating object. The coil picked up any changes in the magnetic field. This signal then passed through a pre-amplifier with a gain of 100 and cut-off value set at 3kHz at 6dB.

6.3.1 Atmospheric Conditions

To verify the results obtained in the simulation, we varied the mass of the object in the experiments. During this set of experiments, the 3D printed object was used (similar to the set-up in fig. 5.2) and to vary the mass a pair of crocodile clips were added. Thus the mass of the suspended object was increased with every iteration.

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

Figure 6.4: Experimental results (a): Voltage vs Time data between $t = 20\text{s}$ to $t = 20.5\text{s}$ for mass = 53g; FFT of the Experimental data for: (b): mass = 53g; (c): mass = 59.911g; (d): mass = 67.827g; (e): mass = 74.494g; (f): mass = 81.212g; (g): mass = 83.582g; (h): mass = 85.940g;

6.3.2 Low Pressure Conditions

We placed the entire set-up in a desiccator and attached a vacuum pump to the system. The pump was then switched on to remove air from the system such that the pressure was reduced to 25KPa , after which we took the measurements. The following results were obtained.

Observations showed that, as we changed the mass of the object, there was no significant change in the frequency of oscillations. This result is something different from what was predicted from the simulations as shown in fig. 6.6.

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

Figure 6.5: Experimental results at 25 KPa (a): Voltage vs Time data between $t = 20$ s to $t = 20.5$ s for mass = 53g; FFT of the Experimental data for: (b): mass = 53g; (c): mass = 59.911g; (d): mass = 67.827g; (e): mass = 74.494g; (f): mass = 81.212g; (g): mass = 83.582g; (h): mass = 85.940g;

Figure 6.6: Mass vs peak frequency of experimental data .

6.3.3 Mass and Current

We also recorded the current values as the mass of the object was varied. For both the conditions, i.e., low pressure and atmospheric, current for a particular mass value were the same. The fig. 6.7 shows the current value recorded during the experiments as the mass of the object was varied.

Figure 6.7: Change in current as mass of the object is varied.

The data was fit with a linear function passing through origin i.e. $y = mx$. This fit gives us the following relation:

$$i = 0.007 * m \quad (6.1)$$

where i is the current in Ampere(A) and m is the mass of the suspended object in grams(g).

6.4 PID Circuit

The data was taken by placing a coil surrounding the levitating object. The coil picked up any changes in the magnetic field. We passed this signal through a pre-amplifier with a gain of 100 and cut-off value set at 3kHz at 6dB.

Figure 6.8: Experimental result for mass = 53g in air with PID circuit. (a): Voltage vs Time data. (b): Data between $t=20$ s to $t=20.5$ s from part (a). (c): FFT of the data in part (a).

Chapter 7

Summary and Conclusion

Levitation through an attractive magnetic force to balance the force of gravity has an unstable equilibrium in the direction of gravity (z-axis), i.e., if the levitating object is above the point of equilibrium, then it moves towards the attractive force and gets stuck to the magnet and if the object is below the point of equilibrium then it falls down. We did not do any extensive analysis of the stability in the plane perpendicular to the direction of gravity (x-y plane). Intuitively we can say that due to the presence of a radial magnetic field, the force in the x-y plane, due to the coil on the object, would be towards the z-axis thus, the levitating object would be stable towards small perturbations in the x-y direction.

7.1 Simulations

The dependence of drain-source voltage (V_{DS}) on drain current (I_D) and gate-source voltage (V_{GS}) was calculated using the data-sheet of the MOSFET used, i.e., STP16NF06. Fig. 7.1 shows a close fit to the data-sheet values; thus, for simulating the dynamic equations, we can assume that the eq. (4.4) is a close approximation of the actual relationship.

Figure 7.1: Output characteristic using the fit equation (eq. (4.4)).

The equations of the motion of the object, i.e., equations (4.1) to (4.5) were simulated using Runge-Kutta 4 method. Initially a fixed time step was used ,i.e., 10^{-4} . But as we

changed the time step the data changed so we finally moved on to adaptive time-step, in this condition the time- step stabilized on $1.25 * 10^{-6}$. All the factors were kept constant except for the mass of the object and the noise factor, which were also varied while keeping the other constant.

When the mass of the object was varied, we observed that the frequency of the oscillations was changing. The relationship between them was of inverse proportionality, i.e., when mass increased the frequency of oscillations decreased. The exact relation between mass and frequency was not obtained, but we give a proportional relationship between the two by equation (4.6) ,i.e., $f \propto \frac{1}{m^{0.45}}$.

We changed the noise in the system by changing the noise factor. When there was no noise in the system, the initial oscillations died down after some time. However, when the noise factor was non-zero, there were sustained oscillations. Increasing the noise above a certain level, on the other hand, will make the object fall as the amplitude of the oscillations will keep on increasing as time progress as shown in fig. 7.2.

Figure 7.2: Comparing the oscillations when noise factor is changed from $nf = 0$ to $nf = 0.05$

7.2 Experiments

We achieve levitation using attractive forces by changing the stability of the system, i.e., from an unstable to a stable system. This was implemented using a feedback loop. The position of the object was sensed using a pair of infra-red LEDs, and accordingly, the current in the coil was adjusted, thus keeping the object levitated.

7.2.1 Varying mass of the object

After which, we tried to replicate one of the results of the simulations, i.e., change in frequency by changing the mass of the object. The object that was used in these set of experiments was the 3-D printed one, as shown in fig. 5.2. The mass of the levitating object was increased by adding a pair of crocodile clips on the opposite wings, thus maintaining the x-y stability. The observations were different from what was predicted by the simulations. There was no change in the peak frequency of oscillations as the mass of the object was varied, as shown in fig. 6.6.

There were lots of assumptions included when the equations of motion of the object were formed for example the exact form of the magnetic field by the coil, the exact relation between V_{DS} , V_{GS} and I_D was also assumed. Thus it can be speculated that the simulation predictions did not come to be in the experiments because of the previously mentioned reasons.

The same set of experiments was also performed by placing the system in a desiccator and maintaining 25KPa of pressure in the system. The change that was observed from the previous experiment was in the noise. In low-pressure condition the noise in the system was reduced, it can be compared by seeing the FFT data of the two experiments with the same mass value. A lot of small peaks that were seen in the FFT data of experiments done in atmospheric conditions were absent from the FFT data of low-pressure set-up. A visual change was also observed, rotation of the object due to air draft was absent in low-pressure condition, and the object appeared to have no visible movement in x-y direction whatsoever. The only motion that existed in this condition was the small oscillations in the z-direction (exact measurements of the z-position were not done).

7.2.2 Mass and Current

Fig. 6.7 shows the dependence of current at which the object has stabilized on the mass of the object, i.e., current increases as the mass of the suspended object increases. This relation between mass and current given by eq. (6.1) ,i.e., $i = 0.007 * m$ can be used to construct a weight balance[12] . With the precise control over current measurement, the mass of an object can be easily calculated with good precision. As there is no mechanical contact between the mass and the system, losses due to friction will also be reduced.

7.2.3 PID Circuit

Comparing the two figures, i.e.,fig. 6.4b and fig. 6.8 one can observe that the FFT of the data with the PID feedback even in atmospheric conditions had a low level of noise compared to the other two data sets. Therefore we can say that this circuit improves the

stability of the system and thus minimizes any unnecessary oscillations, as shown by the comparison in fig. 7.3.

Figure 7.3: Comparing the FFT of the proportional feedback (a) with PID feedback (b)

7.3 Future Perspectives

- As mentioned above in section 7.2.2, one can develop a precise mass measurement system using this set-up. The precision of this system will depend upon the ability to measure the current passing through the coil precisely, after that it is just a linear relation given by eq. (6.1).
- Using the PID circuit in this system, we have minimized the fluctuations in the object. Now that the x-y plane has no movements, we can use this set-up to measure small forces or torques as theoretically there is no opposing force in the x-y plane.

- This report talks about levitating the object using an attractive magnetic force, i.e., instability only in the z-direction (1-D instability). The next plan is to achieve levitation using a repulsive magnetic force. This set-up has a stable equilibrium in the z-direction, but the instability comes in the x-y plane (2-D Instability). The comparison between the two, i.e., attractive and repulsive levitation, might reveal some exciting results considering that attractive levitation has stability in z, but instability in the x-y plane, whereas repulsive levitation has just the opposite stability directions.

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Appendix A

C++ code for simulations

```
1  /*
2  *  final.cpp
3  *
4  *  Created on: 16-Mar-2019
5  *      Author: Yashpal Singh Brar
6  */
7  #include <iostream>
8  #include <fstream>
9  #include <math.h>
10 #include <bits/stdc++.h>
11 #include <cmath>
12 #include <stdlib.h>
13 #include <cstdlib>
14 #include <bits/stdc++.h>
15 #include <vector>
16 #include <algorithm>
17 #include <iterator>
18 #include <stdexcept>
19 #include <iomanip>
20 #include <string>
21 using namespace std;
22
23 // *****
24
25 // Global variables
26 double Vdd = 0; // voltage applied to the feedback
27 double vth = 1.5; // threshold voltage for MOSFET
28 double rc = 12; // resistance of coil
29 double rs = 0.8; // resistance after source
30 double Lc = 30*(pow(10,-3)); // inductance of coil
31 double rp = 20*(pow(10,3)); // resistance after photo-transistor
32 double i0 = 400*(pow(10,-6)); // max current through photo-transistor
33 double za = 0.001; // feedback start
34 double zb = za+0.014; // feedback stop
35 double g = 9.8; // acceleration due to gravity(ms-2)
36 double mu = 1.257*(pow(10,-6)); // permeability of air(SI)
37 double n = 13143; // number of turns per unit length in coil
38 double lc = 0.05; // length of coil(m)
39 double a = 0.0125; // radius of coil(m)
40 double diametre = 0.02; // Diameter of suspended magnet(m)
41 double height = 0.01; // height of suspended magnet(m)
42 double volume = atan(1)*4*(pow(diametre,2))*height/4; // volume of
```

```

    suspended magnet (m)
43 double B = 1; // magnetic strength of suspended magnet(T)
44 double mm = B*volume/mu; // magnetic moment of suspended magnet
45 // *****
46
47 // function declarations
48
49 double RootFinder(double f(double,double), double a1, double b, double m);
50 double RootFinder3(double f(double,double,double), double a1, double b,
    double m,double i);
51 double fun(double x);
52 double gfun(double x);
53 double potds(double vgs,double i);
54 double gs(double x, double i);
55 double f1(double i, double x);
56 double g1(double i, double x,double m);
57 double ssbalf(double z, double m);
58 double ssbalb(double z, double m);
59 double ssbalancez(double m);
60 double sscurr(double vg, double i);
61 double sscurrp(double vg, double i);
62 double sscurrent(double vg);
63 double * rk41(double id,double v,double z,double dt,double noise,double m);
64 double * rk42(double id,double v,double z,double dt,double noise, double m)
    ;
65 double * output(double id,double v,double z,double dt,double noise, double
    m);
66 double * adapt_step(double dt,double step_y,double half_step_y,double
    dble_step_y,double dy_max,double dy_min);
67 double balancef(double x,double i, double m);
68 double balancepoint(double i, double m);
69 // *****
70
71 // *****
72
73 int main()
74 {
75     cout << "Start"<< endl;
76     int preci = 14;
77     double nf=0,m=0,zs=0,vg=0,vgs=0,vov=0,noise=0,rn=0,percent=0;
78     double noisepara [5] = {0.06,0.07,0.08,0.09,0.1}; // noise signal factor
79     double mass[1] = {0}; // mass of suspended object
80     double mi=0.05,dm=0.001;
81     for (int im=0;im<1;im++)
82     {
83         mass [im] = mi+im*dm;
84     }
85     double vcc [1] = {0}; // voltage applied to the feedback
86     double vi=15,dv=1;
87     for (int iv=0;iv<1;iv++)
88     {
89         vcc [iv] = vi+iv*dv;
90     }
91     double tf = 1000; // time length
92     int count = 1;
93     // tolerance factors
94     double dz_max = pow(10,-14);
95     double dz_min = 8*dz_max/10;

```

```

96  int lennoi = (sizeof(noisepara)/sizeof(*noisepara));
97  int lenm = (sizeof(mass)/sizeof(*mass));
98  int lenvcc = (sizeof(vcc)/sizeof(*vcc));
99  double idin = 0,vds=0;
100
101  double* p1;double* p2;double* q1;double* q2;double* q3;double* q4;double*
    r1; double* adapt;
102  double idn[3]={0,0,0},vn[3]={0,0,0},zn[3]={0,0,0};double dt_new=0;
103  int step = 0;
104  double id=0,v=0,z=0,t=0;
105  double prev_progress, total, prev_progress_by_total_percent, t_old=0,
    last_percent=0;
106
107  for (int l=0;l<lennoi;l++){
108
109      nf = noisepara[l];
110
111      for (int i=0;i<lenvcc;i++){
112
113          Vdd = vcc[i];
114
115          for (int j=0;j<lenm;j++){
116              double dt = 0.00001; // initial time-step
117              m = mass[j];
118              zs = ssbalancez(m);
119              z = zs;
120              v = 0;
121
122              if (z<za && z>=0){idin=0;}
123              if (z>zb){
124                  vg = gs(zb,0);
125                  idin = sscurrent(vg);
126                  vgs = gs(zb,idin);
127                  vov = vgs-vth;
128                  if (vov<=0){idin=0;}
129              }
130              if (za<=z && zb>=z){
131                  vg = gs(z,0);
132                  idin = sscurrent(vg);
133                  vgs = gs(z,idin);
134                  vov = vgs-vth;
135                  if (vov<=0){idin=0;}
136              }
137
138              id = idin;
139              int k = 0;
140              t = 0;
141              t_old = 0;
142              prev_progress = j*tf+i*tf*lenm+l*tf*lenm*lenvcc;
143              total = tf*lenm*lenvcc*lennoi;
144              prev_progress_by_total_percent = 100*prev_progress/total;
145
146              char title [40];
147              sprintf(title, "E:/Kantimay/Simulation/c++/data/%d.csv",
count);
148
149              ofstream data;
150              data.open (title);
151              data.clear();

```

```

151
152         do {
153             vgs = gs(z, id);
154             vds = potds(vgs, id);
155             if (k==0){
156                 data <<"Mass"<<" , "<<"Vdd"<<" , "<<" Noise Factor"<<endl;
157                 data <<setprecision (preci)<<"m"<<" , "<<"Vdd"<<" , "<<"nf"<<endl;
158                 data << "Time"<<" , "<<" Position"<<" , "<<" Current"<<" , "<<"GS
159                 "<<" , "<<"DS"<<endl;
160                 data <<setprecision (preci)<<"t"<<" , "<<"z"<<" , "<<"id"<<" , "<<"vgs
161                 "<<" , "<<"vds"<<endl;
162                 k = k+1;
163             }
164
165             rn = ((double) (2.0*rand() / (RANDMAX) - 1.0));
166
167             noise = nf*rn;
168             p1 = output(id, v, z, dt, noise, m);
169             p2 = output(*(p1+0), *(p1+1), *(p1+2), dt, noise, m);
170             idn[0]=*(p2+0); vn[0]=*(p2+1); zn[0]=*(p2+2);
171             if (zn[0]<0){vn[0]=0; zn[0]=0;}
172             q1 = output(id, v, z, dt/2, noise, m);
173             q2 = output(*(q1+0), *(q1+1), *(q1+2), dt/2, noise, m);
174             q3 = output(*(q2+0), *(q2+1), *(q2+2), dt/2, noise, m);
175             q4 = output(*(q3+0), *(q3+1), *(q3+2), dt/2, noise, m);
176             idn[1]=*(q4+0); vn[1]=*(q4+1); zn[1]=*(q4+2);
177             if (zn[1]<0){vn[1]=0; zn[1]=0;}
178             r1 = output(id, v, z, 2*dt, noise, m);
179             idn[2]=*(r1+0); vn[2]=*(r1+1); zn[2]=*(r1+2);
180             if (zn[2]<0){vn[2]=0; zn[2]=0;}
181             adapt = adapt_step(dt, zn[0], zn[1], zn[2], dz_max, dz_min);
182             step = *(adapt+0);
183             dt_new = *(adapt+1);
184             t = t + 2*dt;
185             dt = dt_new;
186             id = idn[step];
187             v = vn[step];
188             z = zn[step];
189             if (z<0)
190             {
191                 v=0;
192                 z=0;
193             }
194             if (t - t_old >= 0.001)
195             {
196                 t_old = t;
197                 data <<setprecision (preci)<<"t"<<" , "<<"z"<<" , "<<"id"<<" , "<<
198                 vgs"<<" , "<<"vds"<<endl;
199                 percent= 100*(t/total) + prev_progress_by_total_percent
200                 ;
201                 if (percent-last_percent >= 0.1)
202                 {
203                     cout << "dt = " << dt << " ; Percent . . . . . " << percent

```

```

204         }
205         while (t<=tf);
206         data.close();
207         cout << "Saved..... " << endl;
208         count = count+1;
209     }
210 }
211 }
212 cout<< "Finished" << endl;
213 return 0;
214 }
215 // *****
216
217 // function definitions
218 double RootFinder(double f(double,double), double a1, double b, double m)
219 {
220     double f_a=f(a1,m), f_b=f(b,m), f_aab=0, f_abb=0, ab=0,ans=0;
221     int iter=1000;
222     double dz=0,z=0,fz=0,faz=0;int zcount=-1;
223     dz = (b-a1)/1000;
224     for (int j=0;j<=1000;j++)
225     {
226         z = a1 + j*dz;
227         fz = f(z,m);
228         faz = f_a*fz;
229         if (faz<=0){zcount = j;}
230     }
231     if (zcount == -1){
232         cout << "Root cannot be found between the given values";
233         exit(0);}
234     b = a1 + zcount*dz;
235     for (int i=0;i<=iter;i++)
236     {
237         f_a = f(a1,m); f_b = f(b,m);
238         ab = (a1+b)/2;
239         f_aab = f_a*f(ab,m);f_abb = f(ab,m)*f_b;
240         if(f_aab<=0){b = ab;}
241         if(f_abb<=0){a1 = ab;}
242     }
243     ans = (a1+b)/2;
244     return ans;
245 }
246 double RootFinder3(double f(double,double,double), double a1, double b,
double m,double i)
247 {
248     double f_a = 0, f_b=0, f_aab=0, f_abb=0, ab=0,fab =0,ans=0;
249     int iter = 1000;
250     for (int i=0;i<=iter;i++)
251     {
252         f_a = f(a1,m,i); f_b = f(b,m,i);fab = f_a*f_b;
253         if (fab>0){
254             cout << "Root cannot be found between the given values";
255             exit(0);}
256         ab = (a1+b)/2;
257         f_aab = f_a*f(ab,m,i);f_abb = f(ab,m,i)*f_b;
258         if(f_aab<=0){b = ab;}
259         if(f_abb<=0){a1 = ab;}
260     }

```

```

261     ans = (a1+b)/2;
262     return ans;
263 }
264 // *****
265 double fun(double x)
266 {
267     double f =0, fac1=0, fac2=0;
268     fac1 = ((lc+x)*(lc+x)+a*a);
269     fac2 = (x*x+a*a);
270     f = (lc+x)/(pow(fac1 ,0.5)) - x/(pow(fac2 ,0.5));
271     return f;
272 }
273 // *****
274 double gfun(double x)
275 {
276     double f=0, fac1=0, fac2=0;
277     fac1 = ((lc+x)*(lc+x)+a*a);
278     fac2 = (x*x+a*a);
279     f = (a*a)*(1/(pow(fac1 ,1.5)) - 1/(pow(fac2 ,1.5)));
280     return f;
281 }
282 // *****
283 double potds(double vgs, double i)
284 {
285     double a1 = 32.85, t1 = 6.5, y = 2.6, t2 = 1.25;
286     double A = 0, b=0, c=0, b1=0, vov=0;
287     vov = vgs-vth;
288     if (vov>0)
289     {
290         c = pow(vgs-vth ,y);
291         A = a1*(1-exp(-c/t1));
292         b1 = A/(A-i);
293         if (A>i){b = t2*log(b1);}
294         if (A<=i){b = Vdd;}
295         if (b<0){b = 0;}
296         if (b>Vdd){b = Vdd;}
297     }
298     else {b=0;}
299     return b;
300 }
301 // *****
302 double gs(double x, double i)
303 {
304     double f = i0*rp*(x-za)/(zb-za) - i*rs;
305     return f;
306 }
307 double f1(double i, double x)
308 {
309     double f = (Vdd-i*(rc+rs)-potds(gs(x, i), i))/Lc;
310     return f;
311 }
312 double g1(double i, double x, double m)
313 {
314     double f = (g + (mm*mu*n/(2*m))*(i*gfun(x)));
315     return f;
316 }
317 // *****
318 double ssbalf(double z, double m)

```

```

319 {
320     double a1 = 32.85,t1 = 6.5,y = 2.6,t2 = 1.25;
321     double curr = 0, gsource=0, vov=0,drain=0;
322     gsource = i0*rp*(z-za)/(zb-za);
323     curr = ((-2*m*g)/(mm*mu*n*gfun(z)));
324     vov = gsource-curr*rs-vth;
325     drain = Vdd-curr*(rc+rs);
326     double f = a1*(1-exp(-(pow(vov,y))/t1))*(1-exp(-drain/t2))-curr;
327     return f;
328 }
329 double ssbalb(double z, double m)
330 {
331     double f = (i0*rp*(z-za)/(zb-za)-((-2*m*g)/(mm*mu*n*gfun(z)))*rs-vth);
332     return f;
333 }
334 double ssbalancez(double m)
335 {
336     double start=za, dz=0.00001,f=0;
337     while (ssbalb(start,m)<0){
338         start = start+dz;
339         if (start>zb){cout << "Cannot balance this mass value";
340             exit(0);}
341     }
342     f = RootFinder(ssbalb, start, zb,m);
343     return f;
344 }
345 // *****
346 double sscurr(double vg, double i)
347 {
348     double f=0, a1 = 32.85,t1 = 6.5,y = 2.6,t2 = 1.25;
349     f = a1*(1-exp(-(pow((vg-i*rs-vth),y))/t1))*(1-exp(-(Vdd-i*(rc+rs))/t2)) -
350         i;
351     return f;
352 }
353 double sscurrp(double vg, double i)
354 {
355     double f=0, a1 = 32.85,t1 = 6.5,y = 2.6,t2 = 1.25;
356     f = a1*(1-exp(-(pow((vg-i*rs-vth),y))/t1))*(-(rc+rs)*(exp(-(Vdd-i*(rc+rs)
357         )/t2))/t2)+a1*(exp(-(pow((vg-i*rs-vth),y))/t1))*(-rs*y*(pow((vg-i*rs-vth)
358         ),(y-1)))/t1)*(1-exp(-(Vdd-i*(rc+rs))/t2)) - 1;
359     return f;
360 }
361 double sscurrent(double vg)
362 {
363     double id=0,vov=0; int n=200;
364     for(int j=0;j<=n;j++){
365         vov = vg-id*rs-vth;
366         if(vov<0){id=0;}
367         else{id = id - (sscurr(vg,id))/(sscurrp(vg,id));}
368     }
369     return id;
370 }
371 // *****
372 double* rk41(double id,double v,double z,double dt,double noise,double m)
373 {
374     static double f[3];
375     double k1 = dt*f1(id,z);
376     double m1 = dt*(g1(id,z,m)+noise);

```

```

374     double n1 = dt*(v);
375     double k2 = dt*f1(id+k1/2, z+n1/2);
376     double m2 = dt*(g1(id+k1/2, z+n1/2, m)+noise);
377     double n2 = dt*(v+m1/2);
378     double k3 = dt*f1(id+k2/2, z+n2/2);
379     double m3 = dt*(g1(id+k2/2, z+n2/2, m)+noise);
380     double n3 = dt*(v+m2/2);
381     double k4 = dt*f1(id+k3, z+n3);
382     double m4 = dt*(g1(id+k3, z+n3, m)+noise);
383     double n4 = dt*(v+m3);
384
385     f[0] = id + (k1+(k2*2)+(k3*2)+k4)/6;
386     f[1] = v + (m1+(m2*2)+(m3*2)+m4)/6;
387     f[2] = z + (n1+(n2*2)+(n3*2)+n4)/6;
388
389     return f;
390 }
391 double* rk42(double id,double v,double z,double dt,double noise, double m)
392 {
393     static double f[3];
394     double k1 = dt*f1(id,zb);
395     double m1 = dt*(g1(id,z,m)+noise);
396     double n1 = dt*(v);
397     double k2 = dt*f1(id+k1/2, zb+n1/2);
398     double m2 = dt*(g1(id+k1/2, z+n1/2,m)+noise);
399     double n2 = dt*(v+m1/2);
400     double k3 = dt*f1(id+k2/2, zb+n2/2);
401     double m3 = dt*(g1(id+k2/2, z+n2/2,m)+noise);
402     double n3 = dt*(v+m2/2);
403     double k4 = dt*f1(id+k3, zb+n3);
404     double m4 = dt*(g1(id+k3, z+n3,m)+noise);
405     double n4 = dt*(v+m3);
406
407     f[0] = id + (k1+(k2*2)+(k3*2)+k4)/6;
408     f[1] = v + (m1+(m2*2)+(m3*2)+m4)/6;
409     f[2] = z + (n1+(n2*2)+(n3*2)+n4)/6;
410
411     return f;
412 }
413 // *****
414 double* output(double id,double v,double z,double dt,double noise, double m)
415 {
416     static double f[3];
417     double* p; double vgs, vov;
418     if (za<=z && zb>=z){
419         vgs = gs(z, id);
420         vov = vgs-vth;
421         if (vov>0){
422             p = rk41(id,v,z,dt,noise,m);
423             for (int j=0;j<3;j++){
424                 f[j] = *(p+j);
425             }
426         }
427         if (vov<=0){
428             f[0] = 0;
429             f[1] = v +dt*(g+noise);
430             f[2] = z +dt*v;
431         }

```

```

432     }
433     if (z<za && z>=0){
434         f[0] = 0;
435         f[1] = v +dt*(g+noise);
436         f[2] = z +dt*v;
437     }
438     if (z>zb){
439         vgs = gs(zb, id);
440         vov = vgs-vth;
441         if (vov>0){
442             p = rk42(id, v, z, dt, noise, m);
443             for (int j=0; j<3; j++){
444                 f[j] = *(p+j);
445             }
446         }
447         if (vov<=0){
448             f[0] = 0;
449             f[1] = v +dt*(g+noise);
450             f[2] = z +dt*v;
451         }
452     }
453     return f;
454 }
455 // *****
456 double* adapt_step(double dt, double step_y, double half_step_y, double
457     dble_step_y, double dy_max, double dy_min)
458 {
459     double dt_new=0; int step=0;
460     static double f[2];
461     double y_min=0, y_max=0;
462     y_max = fabs(1- half_step_y/step_y);
463     y_min = fabs(1- dble_step_y/step_y);
464     if (y_max > dy_max){
465         dt_new = dt/2; // Error is too large; decrease step size.
466         step = 1;
467     }
468     else {
469         if (y_min < dy_min){
470             dt_new = dt*2; // Larger error is acceptable; increase step size.
471             step = 2;
472         }
473         else{
474             dt_new = dt; // This step size is just right.
475             step = 0;
476         }
477     }
478     f[0] = step; f[1] = dt_new;
479     return f;
480 }
481 // *****
482 double balancef(double x, double i, double m)
483 {
484     double f = (mm*mu*n*i/2)*(gfun(x)) + m*g;
485     return f;
486 }
487 double balancepoint(double i, double m)
488 {
489     double x0=0, x1=1;

```

```
489     double f = RootFinder3( balancef ,x0 ,x1 ,m, i );
490     return f;
491 }
492 // *****
```